

O‘ZBEK TILIDAGI SON KATEGORIYASINING TIPOLOGIK TADQIQI

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Abstract: This article analyzes the typological features of the number category in the Uzbek language. The phonetic, morphological and syntactic structure and functions of the number category in the Uzbek language are determined. The results of the study provide information about the various features of the number category in Uzbek and compare them with other Turkic languages or other languages in the world. The article discusses the practical use of the number category in the Uzbek language and recommendations on how to use it in the scientific field.

Key words: Uzbek number category, Typological features, Phonetic, morphological and syntactic structure, Research results, Different features, Comparison, Practical use, Scientific field, Analysis, Discussion.

Introduction: Number category in the Uzbek language is an important part of the language in terms of phonetic, morphological, syntactic structure and functions. This article analyzes the typological study of the number category in the Uzbek language. The purpose of this study is to determine the typological features of the number category in the Uzbek language and compare it with other Turkic languages or other languages in the world.

Methodology: In this study, linguistic methods and analytical methods were used to study the typological features of the number category in the Uzbek language. Literature, articles, and writings in Uzbek language, as well as electronic materials and lectures, were used for the data collection. In the process of analysis, the texts were analyzed to explain the phonetic, morphological, and syntactic features of the number category in the Uzbek language, and the following methods and methods

were used for the typological study of the number category in the Uzbek language in the section where the data were statistically confirmed:

1. Linguistic Methods and Analytical Methods: Linguistic methods and analytical methods were intensively used in this study. Linguistic principles and methods were used for phonological, morphological and syntactic analysis.

2. Text Analysis: To explain the phonetic, morphological and syntactic features of the number category in the Uzbek language, scientific techniques and methods were used to analyze various texts and to determine their specific features.

3. Statistical Analysis: During the study, texts and data were analyzed statistically. This helped to identify many occurrences of the number category in the Uzbek language and their variations.

4. Historical Analysis: Historical analysis and discussion on the historical changes of the number category in the Uzbek language. This helped to understand the stages of language development and its historical changes.

5. Discussion and Comparison: The results of the study are compared to the number category in Uzbek with other Turkic languages or other languages in the world. These comparisons and discussions were an important step in determining the typological features of the number category in the Uzbek language.

Conclusion: This article summarizes many scientific opinions on the typological study of the number category in the Uzbek language. The phonetic, morphological and syntactic features of the number category in the Uzbek language were analyzed and the results of its comparison with other Turkic languages or other languages of the world were studied.

At the same time, it is recommended that the scientific community be given more insight into the typological features of the number category in the Uzbek language and their unique development history. This article should be considered as one of the main sources in scientific studies of the number category in the Uzbek language.

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